

EDUCATION IS A COMMUNITY SPORT

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Talk Overview

(in sport metaphors)

- o Becoming an educator
- o Playing in the academic league
- o Playing for industry
- o Synthesizing similarities & contrasts

Becoming an educator

Scientist

Reluctant Educator,
Student

Bioinformatician + Educator + Education Program Director

DARTMOUTH

ILLINOIS

HARVARD
UNIVERSITY

AstraZeneca
What science can do

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PLAYING IN THE ACADEMIC LEAGUE

“The bicycle” – good for going far

An international consensus on effective, inclusive, and career-spanning short-format training in the life sciences and beyond.

Williams J. J. et al (2023)

PLOS ONE 18(11): e0293879.

<https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0293879>

Training Focus

- Short Format Training following “The Bicycle Principles”
- Using the Carpentries philosophy of open and collaborative content on Github
- Topics: Coding skills, Data analysis methods for bioinformatics/genomics, Data Management
- Geared towards biologists with a biomedical focus

Email: hbctraining@hsph.harvard.edu

Webpage: <http://bioinformatics.sph.harvard.edu/training/>

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Essential Communities

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PLAYING FOR INDUSTRY

Training Focus

- Short Format Training
- On-Demand Training
- Topics: Coding skills, Data Science methods, Data Management, Collaboration Skills
- Geared towards many different demographics interested in Data Science; from generalists to lab scientists to data scientists to leaders
- Many more practical considerations, such as ability to commit time to learning, ever-changing company focus, large spectrum of learner demographics

SYNTHESIZING SIMILARITIES & CONTRASTS

SIMILARITIES

Topics

- Coding (R, Python)
- Data Management
- Analysis Methodology
- Machine Learning
- Experimental design
- Statistical Principles

Oversight structure (partially)

Large number of learners are lab biologists

Community

- Internal communities of practice
- Involvement in external communities

Challenge

- Learner Motivation

CONTRASTS

Industry

Time for learning & development

- Time to practice new skills can be challenging
- More demand for self-paced learning

Topics

- Coding (SAS, JMP)
- AI
- Collaboration and efficiency

Many stakeholders

Larger audience

Academia

Basic research focus

Less diverse audience

Less funding for external solutions to training needs

What can be done better?

Industry can be better about contributions back to Open Science and Open Communities

Paying or appropriately rewarding “volunteers” for their efforts and contribution

Learners can have more dedicated time for development

Developing trainer Communities in Industry

What else?

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What can be done better in the education + communities context within academia and/or industry?

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Essential skills and mindset for Educators and Community Members

Collaboration skills!

Identifying your strengths/weaknesses

Valuing others work

Ability to adapt

1. Adapting materials for your needs
2. Adapting direction based on stakeholder input

Knowing when to consider a stakeholder idea and when not to

Contributing to communities

What else?

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What do you think are the essential skills and mindset needed to be in an education-focused community?

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THANK YOU!

Harvard Chan Bioinformatics Core
HPCBio, UIUC
The Carpentries
Life Science Trainers
GobleT
Harvard Catalyst
Boston Women in Bioinformatics
Harvard Women In Tech

Organizers!
Audience members!

Meeta Mistry, Harvard Univ
Mary Piper, Pfizer
Gabriella Rustici, AZ
Chris Fields, UIUC
Jason Williams, CSHL
Shannan Ho Sui, Harvard Univ
Robert Freeman, Harvard Univ

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Audience Q&A

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